

Role of Education to Meet Global Challenges

Rashmi Dhar

Associate Professor

D.A.V. (P.G.) College Dehradun

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Abstract

Values lead to the aims of human life and act as standard bearers toward achieving these aims. Aims and values are closely related and one without the other may not have any significance, Values are categorized in four spheres. These are individual, national, religious and global which are influenced by the Family, the State, Religious institutions and World institutions respectively. These are the 'pressure groups' which foster various values among human beings. The values as work, competition, individualism, socio-economic success and self dependence are inculcated through the Family Values of patriotism, common heritage, citizen responsibilities and the national identity are imbibed through The State and Religion inculcates values of devotion and faith. Socio-economic and educational world institutions serve to promote values of Pluralism, tolerance, concern for the eco-system, global peace and friendship, liberalism and globalization. All these four 'pressure groups' are formal and informal agencies of education. In spite of the efforts of these educational institutions lots of problems are faced by societies and social groups causing challenges at global scenario. Mainly the problems faced are (i) Groupism (ii) Environmental catastrophes (iii) Dictatorships (iv) Breakdown of the family (v) Resistance to change (vi) Dangers magnified. Though the societies have gathered so much knowledge power and ability, still so many problems are faced by the societies, the question arises do we need better controls or do we need to change direction? Education is the only tool in the hands of the 'pressure groups'. We should modify the vision of education. This could be inculcated to produce kind of mind we require to solve these problems. There is no uniform prescription for all countries and cultures. At macro level or at international level human minds or Psyche should be of the type (i) global, not a nationalistic mind (ii) committed to human, not economic development only (iii) An inquiring, not conforming mind (iv) co-operative, not competitive mind (v) A learning not an acquisitive mind (vi) A mind, scientific and religion (vii) concerned with the art of living (viii) A holistic mind. In new vision, education should not only take the responsibility to impart information and skill but also to awaken sensitivity and creativity in the mind of the child. Education is a tool to transform consciousness of human mind to face challenges at individual as well as at global level.

Keywords: Groupism, Environmental Catastrophes, Dictatorship, Holistic Mind, Art of Living.

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In spite of the efforts of these educational institutions lots of problems are faced by societies and social groups causing challenges at global scenario. Mainly the problems faced are (i) Groupism (ii) Environmental catastrophes (iii) Dictatorships (iv) Breakdown of the family (v) Resistance to change (vi) Dangers magnified.

- (i) **Groupism** : There are racial, national, religious, linguistic, economic, political and professional groups and individual of each group feels rivalry with other groups and cares for the security and progress of his own group. There is too much exploitation, cheating and destruction causing insecurity among societies leading towards wars, terrorism riots and militancy.
- (ii) **Environmental Catastrophes**: Nature is regarded as something meant for our use. The attitude of treating nature as resources to be exploited is the root cause of many problems faced these days e.g. depletion of ozone layer, global warming, industrial pollution, soil erosion, nuclear fall outs and over population. We need to live in harmony with the rest, regarding all as friends and not resources. Until and unless the attitude towards nature is not changed we will face more and more catastrophes. We may have better computers and faster trains or plans but we will not have fresh air to breathe and new diseases caused by the disequilibrium will make life not worth living.
- (iii) **Dictatorship** : It curbs freedom of expression, political freedom, freedom to grow, freedom to question, to think and to write. People are told what to do and not to do. So long it is believed that Power is meant to exploit the weak which is an uncivilized use of power causing destruction and domination. Education must concern itself with bringing about the right use of power by changing the relationship of mankind with power. Let them think and believe that Might is not right. The spirit of democracy needs to be inculcated in every individual to meet out the problem of dictatorship faced at national or global level.
- (iv) **Breakdown of Family**: The institution of marriage and family ensures responsible up bringing of next generation. Breaking of joint family structure, concept of nuclear families, busy and stressful life patterns of parents have deprived the children of next generation from getting their due share of upbringing. This has increased the number of problem children and delinquents and also has bad effect on mental health of children and adolescents with rise in percentage of depressive frustrated and rebellious children of next generation. Obviously the right approach is not followed. A need to rethink where we have gone wrong.
- (v) **Resistance to Change** : society tends to replicate itself. Prejudices and illusions tend to continue from one generation to the next along with the problems associated with them. There is too much inertian in society. The only way to change the resistance is by creating inquisitive minds, inquiring not only the scientific questions but also the social, moral and religious questions.
- (vi) **Dangers Magnified** : There is history of wars and rivalry for thousands of years but now we cannot afford these any more. Nuclear bombs are many times more dangerous to swords, bows and arrows. It is a high time we should develop attitude to use advancement due to science and technology for human welfare instead o human destruction globally.

Though the societies have gathered so much knowledge power and ability, still so many problems are faced by the societies, the question arises do we need better controls or do we need to change direction? Education is the only tool in the hands of the 'pressure groups'. We should modify the vision of education. This could be inculcated to produce kind of mind we require to solve these problems. There is no uniform prescription for all countries and cultures.

In spite of industrialisation and advancement of Science and Technology we are still facing so many problem globally. We need to re-think our priorities in education and question our vision with which we have been working so far. Our vision of education at present is to develop a human being who is intelligent knowledgeable, hardworking, efficient, disciplined, smart, successful and a leader in 'his field' of work but without love and compassion. The lop-sided development of the individual has

caused all the problems. Education should impart wisdom along with knowledge. Education should be provided in such a manner that should transform the mind in such a manner that instead of thinking ourselves as 'I' we should believe in 'We'. Education should aim at producing the kind of mind having following characteristics.

These are-

- (a) **Global not a nationalistic mind** : There should be global understanding. A global mind does not believe in 'might is right'. With democratic means issues between nations can be settled. Problems should be solved with global understanding.
- (b) **Committed to human and not economic development** - Education should not consider children as resources for economic development rather its concern should be to develop all aspects of human being so that they live happily and creatively as a part of whole universe.
- (c) **An inquiring, not conforming mind** - The child must be free to make mistakes and learn for itself without the constant fear of being scolded. The mind would be rational, flexible and open to change
- (d) **Co-operative, not competitive mind** - The sense of competition that is being encouraged in children leads to envy, jealousy and rivalry. It causes division and destroys love and friendship. Cooperation is the basic of democracy. We are all interrelated and interdependent and work for the welfare of the whole community.
- (e) **A learning, not an acquisitive mind** - Intelligence is the ability to learn for oneself learning is endless. It is important to create a mind that which is able to discriminate between what is true and what is not true.
- (f) **A scientific and religious mind**- Aim of education should be to create a mind that is simultaneously scientific and religious i.e. precise, rational and inquiring and at the same time has a sense of beauty, sensitivity and humility. Understanding oneself is as important as understanding the world. Education should make individuals understand their relationship with nature, ideas, fellow human beings and society.
- (g) **Concern with the art of living** - A mind that is constantly worried, bored, envious or frustrated cannot lead a qualitatively superior life. Education not for economic development but for human development must concern with the happiness of the individual as a whole, in which physical well being and comfort are small but necessary part. When children are taught to work for a reward and not for the joy of working, they are taught to separate work from pleasure. The art of living consists in enjoying everything one does, irrespective of the results it offers.
- (h) **A holistic mind** At present education is meant for producing specialists but it should not be at the cost of understanding the meaning to live fully. All the three domains of Personality should be equally developed. Not only the Intellectual Quotient (I.Q.) should be the target point of Education but it should also cater to the development of Emotional Quotient (E.Q.) and Spiritual Quotient (S.Q.) There are several difficulties in imparting such education. Our minds are conditioned into the old system, the old vision. We must learn to break from the past, adopt new methods to achieve new aims and objectives of Education for developing creative minds. Education must concern itself with the inner transformation of the human consciousness. Education must enrich the system with the growth of the soul. There must be a change of heart which will alone bring profound change in socialism, nationalism, internationalism. Transvaluation of values only can lead to Psychological unity of human mind universally and result in peace, economical well-being, general security, cultural, social, intellectual activity and progress.

In new vision, education should not only take the responsibility to impart information and skill but also to awaken sensitivity and creativity in the mind of the child. Education is a tool to transform consciousness of human mind to face challenges at individual as well as at global level.

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